

Environmental Determinants of Health: A Study of Problem Gambling in Montreal

by

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ABSTRACT

Social and physical environments provide settings that can be more or less supportive of risky behaviours. The form of gambling linked most strongly to problem gambling, video lottery terminal (VLT) use, is used to study the link between environment and behaviour. First, people living closer to VLTs were hypothesized to be more likely to gamble due to greater accessibility. Second, social mechanisms, such as social norms, were hypothesized to cause spatial clustering of gambling prevalence rates. Data from a telephone survey of Montreal residents (Ladouceur 2004) were modeled hierarchically in a logistic multilevel model with 2007 individuals in 49 residential areas. Results show that respondents living in the bottom tertile of physical accessibility are almost half as likely to use VLTs as the remaining respondents. Also, VLT use prevalence rates show spatial clustering, even after controlling for compositional characteristics and physical accessibility. Environmental factors, both physical and social, are deemed to be intrinsic to problem gambling etiology and to health in general.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Since the liberalization of Canadian gambling laws in 1969, the accessibility of gambling opportunities has greatly increased across Canada. In Quebec, video lottery terminals (VLTs) were introduced in 1994 and have since spread to bars across the province. Today, VLTs are considered controversial as a form of revenue generation for states worldwide because of their strong relation to problem gambling (Doiron et al. 2001). VLT users are ten times more likely than the population as a whole to report probable pathological or problematic gambling behaviour (21% among VLT users compared to 2% within the entire population). Problem gambling, in turn, is linked to a wide range of other mental health and family problems, including suicide, bankruptcy and marital problems (Korn et al. 1999, 2002).

Experts, as well as the Montreal public (Aubin 2002) agree that at least part of the reason VLTs are so hazardous must be due to their high accessibility. The purpose of this study is to measure the influence that social and physical environmental factors may have on VLT use, in the Montreal context.

The study of the association between the social and physical environment and VLT use both draws from and contributes to a number of different relevant fields of research. First, from a prevention perspective, this study may help indicate whether community-based primary prevention of VLT use is an appropriate means of preventing the negative effects of problem gambling. Second, from a broader social science perspective, this study will advance research on the specific mechanisms linking individual socio-economic status, environment and health (Tugwell 2004, Macintyre 2002). Finally, and most narrowly, studying environmental effects on VLT use will help clarify problem gambling etiology. The links between VLT use, problem gambling and

health have already been established (Doiron et al. 2001) and reviewed (Korn 1999, 2002) elsewhere.

Figure 1 shows a conceptual framework of problem gambling from an environmental or “population health” perspective. This model differs from those used in psychological studies (Figure 2) because it studies VLT use, rather than problem gambling and because it incorporates environmental factors. Generally, the study of gambling (rather than problem gambling) is limited to some public health reports (e.g. Chevalier et al. 2001), few of

Figure 1. The scope of VLT use within the population health perspective.

Figure 2. The interests of psychologists in problem gambling.

which are published in peer-reviewed journals. The study of accessibility is limited to studies of the establishment of casinos on community problem gambling rates (e.g. Jacques et al. 2000).

Knowing whether there are variations in the rate of VLT use across spatially based population segments will add to the current literature on gambling, as to our knowledge, no one has yet taken this approach. Gambling literature has tended to estimate prevalence of problem gambling across very large study areas and groups, such as Manitoban adolescents (Wiebe 1999), or university students in Quebec City (Ladouceur 1998). However, Lesieur (1994) calls for the study of gambling problems within specific subpopulations, due to the high prevalence rates in certain population segments citing, among others, prisoners. Estimating rates of VLT across multiple subpopulations will

take this perspective a step further. This study will allow for identification of at risk subpopulations.

1.1 Objectives and Hypotheses

The purpose of this paper is to assess whether aspects of the physical and social environment are associated with the propensity for individuals to use VLTs. This task is simplified by dividing the environment into a physical and social dimension. The physical dimension refers to the physical accessibility of VLTs, as measured using distance. With respect to the physical environment we ask whether the spatial distribution of VLTs influences VLT use. It is hypothesized that people living closer to VLTs are more likely to gamble. (2) The social dimension refers to all other aspects of the residential environment, including the influence of peers and social norms. With respect to the social environment, we ask whether VLT users tend to cluster spatially. It is hypothesized that VLT use prevalence rates vary significantly between residential areas due to differing social norms with regards to VLT use.

In summary, a model of VLT use is presented based on two measurements, first a distance to VLT measurement and second a measurement of clustering of VLT users.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is presented in two sections. The first section reviews literature on the influence of environment on health behaviours and the second reviews literature on gambling. Given that no research has looked at the effect of environment on gambling behaviour (Korn 1999, 2002), perspectives from the more theoretically driven population health research field (Macintyre 2002) and the health behaviours (Duncan 1999, Frolich 2002 and Wilcox 2003) field will be used. The link between VLT use and problem gambling has already been established, (Doiron et al. 2001, Korn 1999, Korn 2002) and will only briefly be reviewed.

Second, the gambling literature will be reviewed. The evidence of the influence of physical accessibility and social environment effects on gambling behaviour and problem gambling will be summarized. As well, individual psychological factors thought to be relevant to VLT use will be reviewed. The interest in individual factors is to determine characteristics of individuals putting them at risk of VLT use which may also be related to residential location: so-called confounders (see Figure 1).

2.1 Environment and health related behaviours

Large inequalities in physical conditions and the distribution of disease and mortality within industrial era cities led the forefathers of public health to understand the environment, social and physical, as important to the health of individuals (Frank 1995). The improvement of physical conditions, starting after the second World War, veered health researchers away from ecological perspectives, as environments were improved. The attribution of variations in health to individual behavioural characteristics became a dominant model (Macintyre 2000). However, recently, several fields of research have fuelled a return to environmental perspectives, most notably the population health

perspective and its interest in health inequalities. Health inequalities research has emphasized the continued existence of large inequalities in life-expectancy across social groups in developed countries, even after the improvement of physical conditions of the poor (Kawachi 2002). Many researchers looking at health inequalities hypothesize that the local environment factors, both social and physical explain, at least in part, the relation between low socio-economic status and poor health (Kawachi 2002).

Within the theoretical field of population health is health behaviours research. This is the study of behavioural mechanisms linking environment to health. In particular, research on ecological determinants of smoking provide an analogous behaviour to VLT use, in that it is an unhealthy behaviour with hypothesized individual and environmental determinants.

The population health field draws on the theories of Macintyre (2002), who has created a typology of three types of place-effects consisting of compositional, contextual and collective effects. The first, compositional effects, refers to the effect of individual constituents on the aggregate health of a place. This is in fact, not a place-effect, but is the individual effect on the health of a place, a confounder with respect to place-effects. The second, the contextual explanation, refers to aspects of the local physical environment that effect behaviour, and is sometimes referred to as "opportunity structures". The third type of place-effect is the influence of the social environment, including social norms, social capital, and their effects on health of aggregates of individuals. Macintyre qualifies this classification by saying that these three forms of explanation should not be considered independent. Composition influences context and the collective aspect of places and vice-versa. Nevertheless, much empirical research

continues to look for independent influences of context on health (e.g. Frolich 2002, Duncan 1999).

Kawachi (2002) extends these ideas. The notion of contextual heterogeneity is the idea that places with high health status for one group, may have low health status for another. Thus, what may appear to be an even distribution of health status across a whole population, may vary markedly within certain sub groups. This concept is descriptive: the underlying process is an individual-contextual interaction also known as a modifying place-effect (Wilcox 2003). A modifying place effect is an effect of place on the relation between an individual's "characteristics" and their health. For example, if men generally gamble more than women, but in a certain place, we observe that they gamble significantly less, we would call this a modifying place-effect.

Wilcox (2003) summarizes three etiological explanations regarding the influence of ecological factors on smoking: collective functioning, contagion and differential affiliation. Collective functioning controls smoking behavior when strong norms regarding the acceptability or unacceptability of a behaviour impose informal social control which in turn influences use.

With regards the influence of collective functioning on gambling, Morton (2003) shows that gambling problems that "ravaged" Chinese migrant workers in Canadian Chinatowns in the late 19th century and early 20th centuries were partly attributable to inapplicable social norms regarding the influence of gambling on family members. Male Chinese migrant workers, who had no families, were allowed to gamble because authorities saw nothing wrong with gambling for the individual with no family. Thus, gambling proceeded unregulated in the Chinese community. It seems that norms regarding gender roles and familial responsibility may play a significant role with respect

to gambling behaviour. Chinese gambling seems to have been originated from a breakdown of the collective functioning of the community, due to inapplicable social norms.

Contagion occurs when an activity spreads through peer networks. When a behaviour spreads by contagion, high concentrations of a behaviour are found within some peer networks and low concentration within others. Differential affiliation, the third mechanism, describes situations whereby certain subpopulations in certain places are more or less likely to participate in a certain behaviour through differential affiliation.

2.2 *Gambling Literature*

Literature on gambling is replete with studies by psychologists on the individual risk factors associated with VLT use, but there has been little research on gambling from an ecological perspective (exceptions Morton 2003, Dixey 1987, Hogan 1986). Framing of gambling as a public health issue has begun (Korn 1999, 2000, 2002), but empirical research within the public health field has yet to address the ecological determinants of gambling problems. Nevertheless, governmental commissions (Productivity Commission 1999) and public perception (Aubin 2002) suggest that accessibility may be an important reason for the high incidence of VLT use.

This section begins with a review of the state of the distribution of VLTs across industrialized nations. Evidence pertaining to the link between availability of gambling and problem gambling will then be reviewed. Third, the broad field of research that has looked at individual risk factors pertaining to problem gambling, will be reviewed. Finally, the history and current distribution of VLTs in Quebec will be summarized.

2.2.1 Gaming machines nationally and internationally

VLTs are a type of electronic gaming machine (EGM) for which the speed of play is fast, and the maximum bet is quite high, allowing the gambler to wager (and lose) money very quickly. The maximum average rate of loss for a machine is a measure of how much a gambler can expect to lose if he or she bets the maximum wager, at the maximum rate the machine allows, for one full hour. It is found by multiplying the maximum amount one can wager in one hour by the payout rate. The Australian Productivity Commission (1999) provides a typology of gaming machines found internationally based on this measure. The only EGMs found in Canada are VLTs, and these are classed in the most hazardous category, with an average maximum rate of loss of about \$150 an hour. Canada is not exceptional in that other countries have similar high intensity machines, including the United States, France and Australia. On the other hand, some countries, such as Japan and the UK, only have lower intensity EGMs.

Different countries regulate access to machines differently. High intensity machines in most countries are either banned, or are limited to a few limited access locations such as riverboats, and casinos. Australia and Canada are exceptions to the rule, in that high-intensity machines are widely distributed.

In terms of the distribution of these machines nationally, about a third of VLTs found in Canada (38 000) are located in Quebec. Thus Quebec is very similar to Australia in terms of the availability of high-intensity machines in highly accessible locations.

2.2.2 Link between availability and use

Evidence from other states suggests an association between prevalence of problem gambling and availability of gambling opportunities, especially to high intensity

electronic gaming machines. The evidence pertaining most specifically to VLTs as they are distributed in Quebec originates from Australia.

A longitudinal meta-analysis from North America (Shaffer et al. 1997) showed an increasing trend of availability and use. A study of Quebec City looked at the effect of the development of a casino, and found a significant increase in gambling among residents of the city, when compared to a control (Jacques et al. 2001). However, this evidence pertains to accessibility at a city-wide scale. In Australia, a significant correlation between per capita electronic gaming machines (EGMs per capita) and prevalence of problem gambling was found (Productivity Commission 1999) at the state level. In the same study, no significant relation between the total availability (including other forms of gambling) of gambling and problem gambling was found.

2.2.3 Individual traits of gamblers

Most research on gambling falls into one of two categories. First, from a psychological perspective, theoretically informed researchers try to uncover the link between specific psychological traits and problem gambling (Korn 1999). Second, many prevalence studies from a joint public and psychological perspective estimate the prevalence of gambling and problem gambling across large populations. These studies look at the individual traits collected in most social science surveys, including sex, age, gender, income, occupation, etc. Chevalier (2001), summarizes some of the findings of such population based studies. Studies taking a more explanatory approach to gambling and problem gambling are less common and older. The explanations with respect to age, class, and gender are briefly summarized.

Chevalier (2001) summarizes some of the correlates of gambling. In short, men gamble more than women, in the general population, as well as within subpopulations

including university students and heroin addicts. Gamblers are generally older, but it is the young that are more likely to show problem gambling behaviour. Gambling is also unevenly distributed across groups defined by race, ethnicity and birthplace, but no universal relation exists.

Age differences in propensity to gamble are attributable to aging and cohort effects (McPherson 1983 in Mok 1991). Aging effects refer to changes within the individual as he or she ages. Several different theories suggest mechanisms that decrease the likelihood for an individual to play as he or she ages, including Erikson's Eight Stages of Development, Self-Presentation, Activity, Disengagement and Continuity. Cohort effects are effects on gambling behaviour that are unrelated to age, but are mainly related to changing social context.

For centuries, gambling has been identified as more prevalent in working class populations than in wealthier or poorer populations. Historians and sociologists have explained this in numerous ways. Hogan (1986) explains that "...workers who enjoy a small but steady cash-flow, on a short cycle of investment and return, have the liquid assets required for regular gambling" (134). Hogan contrasts the opportunity costs of gambling for miners and cowboys on the American frontier, to that of farmers. For farmers, returns were required to absorb costs over the winter and during the growing season, and farmers also had opportunities to invest in additional equipment (or labour) and yield larger profits the next year. Thus, the opportunity-costs for gambling were high. For miners and cowboys, on the other hand, who owned little and who were paid in short cycle, opportunity costs were low. Thus, it would seem that commitments to long-term projects, such as home-ownership mortgages, would tend to decrease gambling. On the other hand, a "small but steady cash-flow" would encourage gambling, because such a

salary would not be large enough to enable home ownership, but would but would still be enough to enable participation.

Gambling has historically been a very gender specific activity (Morton 2003). While some forms of gambling, such as bingo, are generally adopted by women (Dixey 1983), others are more prevalent among men. Most research on VLTs has shown that men tend to participate more in this form of gambling.

2.2.4 The History of VLTs in Montreal

The literature shows that the distribution of gambling opportunities has increased since the liberalization of gambling in the 60's. Gambling availability has increased in two steps, the first with the initial decriminalization of gambling in 1969 and the second with the advent of electronic gaming machines, and their widespread distribution since the early 90s. The purpose of this section is to review the history of gambling in the Canadian and, specifically, the Montreal context.

The passage of the omnibus bill, C-150, in 1969, was an extensive revision of the Criminal Code. Bill C-150 included many articles addressing many areas including abortion, homosexuality and gambling. With respect to the latter, the legislation permitted both federal and provincial governments to operate lotteries of any size. Quebec was the first province to set up a lottery, in 1970. Several years later, the federal government organized the Olympic Lottery hoping to help pay for the 1976 games in Montreal. This led to federal-provincial jurisdictional disputes and in August 1976, the federal government withdrew from the lotteries altogether in return for an annual inflation adjusted cash transfer from the provinces. This was formalized in a 1985 amendment to the Criminal Code.

New Brunswick introduced the first legal VLTs in Canada in 1991. In 1992, the Quebec government gave Loto-Quebec the mandate to exploit a video lottery system and in 1993 a regulatory body called the Société des lotteries vidéo du Québec was created. The first VLTs were put into circulation in 1994 and by 1996 there were 15,300 machines across the province. For the following 5 years the VLT population remained stable until May 2001 and March 2003 when Loto-Quebec announced it would reduce the number to 14,300 and then 10,500. Nevertheless, revenues from VLTs have continued to increase since they were first installed such that VLTs currently contribute more than half of Loto-Quebec's profits.

2.2.5 The Distribution of VLTs in Montreal

The widespread introduction of VLTs into bars and taverns across Quebec in 1994 has meant that VLTs are accessible to pretty much any adult wishing to use one. Nevertheless, local variations in the concentration of VLTs remain. Gilliland et al. (submitted) have shown that VLTs in Montreal are more prevalent in neighbourhoods where the average educational attainment is low, even after controlling for the prior distribution of bars. In fact, bars are more likely to locate in low-education areas and VLTs are more likely to locate in bars in working class areas. As well, the study showed that traditionally wealthy boroughs, Westmount and Outremont, are dry towns, and thus have no VLTs. The western suburbs of Montreal have very few VLTs, while the northern suburban municipality (Laval) and the east end of the Montreal island have a disproportionately large number. This pattern of VLTs concentrating in disadvantaged areas is similar to that described in Melbourne, Australia by Marshall and Baker (2000).

As well, this description of the distribution of VLTs in Montreal corresponds to the historically uneven distribution of gambling facilities across Montreal. Morton (2003)

reports that, among gambling facilities raided by police between 1942 and 1950, no address connected gambling to the wealthy neighbourhoods of Westmount and Outremont and only one was listed in the middle-class neighbourhood of NDG.” Instead, locations were concentrated in the red-light district around St-Catherine and St-Laurent, areas around the main train stations, downtown theatre and nightclub district and the precincts centered on the working class commercial streets of Mont-Royal and St-Laurent. This description echoes that from Gilliland et al. (submitted), who found that municipal bylaws restricting the establishment of bars, have simultaneously prevented the establishment of VLTs.

2.2.6 Factors controlling the distribution of VLTs

In Quebec, bars obtained VLT licenses (VLTL) while they were being distributed in the 1994-1996 period. Norris (2002) provides an overview of the VLT licensing process.

When the VLT licenses were first being distributed, in early 1994, the number of VLT licenses that could be distributed was tied to the floor space and to the number of liquor licenses. Only one VLT license could be obtained per liquor license. Bar owners could however, obtain more than one

liquor license for their bar by building new pseudo-bars and subdividing the bar into smaller compartments. As well, later in 1994, a new government abolished the limit to the number of VLT

Figure 3. Players controlling distribution of gambling opportunities.

licenses allowed per unit of floorspace. The number of VLTs an owner wished to obtain was thus dependent on their willingness and ability to pay for the required renovations.

The Loto-Quebec officials sanctioned this subdividing of bars (Norris 2002). Some bar owners established mini-casinos with up to 40 VLTs.

There has been relatively little movement of VLTs in Montreal since 1994. One would expect that a large proportion of the VLTs distributed in 1994 are in nearly the same locations today. This somewhat immobile distribution is quite different compared to the state of Victoria in Australia, where all 27,000 of the state's EGMs are controlled by only two private machine operators. Machines can and are moved based on the commercial decisions of the operators (Marshall 2001).

3 METHOD

3.0.1 Data and sources

The data on gambling was obtained from a provincial survey of gambling behaviour performed for the Institut Nationale de Santé Publique du Québec (Ladouceur 2004), through one of the researchers, Serge Chevalier. Chevalier provided all the respondent socio-demographic variables, all of the variables related to VLT use, and the six digit respondent postal code for those respondents living on the islands of Montreal or Laval.

For the provincial survey, the phone numbers were randomly generated from a provincial database. The calling was performed by a private polling firm between May and November 2002. In total, calls to 15 679 homes were made, of which 8 842 interviews were conducted, a response of 56.4%. Only respondents over 18 were interviewed.

Of the 2493 respondents reportedly living on the islands of Montreal and Laval, 2088 provided their full six-digit postal code. These respondents were assigned longitude and latitude positions (geocoded) based on the centroid of their postal code (using Geopoint): of the 2088 respondents who reported living in Montreal or Laval and who gave their six-digit postal code, 2008 matches were found with valid postal codes that were in the study area (some gave off-island postal codes). One of these respondents did not answer the question pertaining to VLT use, and was eliminated. Of the final sample of 2007, 2% were coded by 1996 enumeration area (EA) centroid while the remaining 98% were coded by postal code (PC) centroid.

The response rate of the subsample of respondents who gave their postal code is approximated by the global response rate multiplied by the portion that gave a postal code (whether in the study area or not), yielding 47.2%.

Data on bars and taverns was obtained from the Regie des Alcools, des Courses et des Jeux (RACJ) through the health geography laboratory at McGill University. This database was composed of all establishments with liquor licenses allowing for the sale of alcohol without a meal. For each of these establishments, postal code, municipality and the number of VLT licenses (VLTLs) were listed. Recall that one VLT license allows a bar owner to operate up to five VLTs.

All establishments on the islands of Montreal and Laval, as well as those within 10km of the islands were plotted. Establishments on the island of Montreal and in Laval were geocoded by exact address (1761 successes, all initial failures were geocoded manually), while sites off-island were geocoded to postal code centroid (489 successes, 4 failures which were excluded from the analysis). The off-island sites were added to prevent an “edge effect” in the measure of geographic VLT accessibility. An edge effect, in these circumstances, is an exaggerated measurement of distance to VLTs for respondents living near the edge of the islands, due the closer VLTs on the mainland, when off island VLTs are not included in the measurement of respondent-VLT distances. The final number of establishments was 2250.

3.0.2 Neighbourhood Definition

The neighbourhood units in this study are geo-political areas (boroughs) composed of: (1) sub-municipal “planning areas” for the pre-merged City of Montreal (merged 2001); (2) ex-municipal boundaries of the pre-merged Island of Laval (merged 1969), and; (3) ex-municipal boundaries for the merged City of Montreal, outside of the pre-merged City of Montreal.

3.0.3 Outcome Variable

The question pertaining to VLT gambling asked “have you, in the last twelve months, spent money on a VLT outside of a casino?” Of the 2008 respondents, 2007 responded to the question, of which 166 answered yes, the remaining responded that they had not used a VLT. Thus, the global prevalence of VLT use was 8.3% for this study area. This rate of VLT use is similar to that from the entire study region from which the study originated.

3.0.4 Individual Level Predictors

The following individual level variables were included in the dataset: sex, age, whether the respondent was living with a partner, mother tongue, birthplace, religion, educational attainment, employment status, home ownership status, household revenue, whether a member of the family was perceived as being a problem gambler.

3.0.5 Distance

The straightline distance of each respondent to each establishment with a liquor license was measured using the coordinates of the respondents and the bars. Matrix algebra was used to calculate a distance matrix with 2007 rows and 2250 columns (2007 by 2250). In this matrix rows corresponded to respondents while each column specified a certain liquor establishment. For each respondent, the distance and the number of VLT licenses (VLTL) for the nearest 200 liquor establishments were retained, leaving a 2007 by 200 matrix.

3.0.6 Conceptual Framework for the measurement of geographic accessibility

Section 2.2.2 (p. 12) reviewed the literature that shows the link between the availability of gambling opportunities and problem gambling. The Australian Productivity Commission's study shows the relationship between per capita electronic gaming machine (EGM) availability and problem gambling are significant at a large scale of analysis. At

such a large scale of analysis, the availability of VLTs in one state could be assumed to not influence the availability to respondents in other states. However, as the scale of analysis decreases, the degree to which the respondents may access opportunities outside of their area increases, to the point where per capita EGM availability would become meaningless as a measure of accessibility, since accessibility in adjacent areas is so intertwined. The gravity model is used to overcome the challenge of quantifying accessibility at a small scale by creating separate measures of accessibility for individual respondents based on the VLTs in their surroundings. Section 2.1 reviewed the mechanisms whereby accessibility could influence use of VLTs. Macintyre (2002) proposed contextual effects as those aspects of the physical environment that influence health outcomes and collective effects as those aspects of the social environment that could influence health. Let local concentration (geographic accessibility at the individual scale) be a measure of VLT opportunity structures, while borough concentration (geographic accessibility at the scale of the borough) be a measure of the collective social norms regarding the acceptability of VLTs. It is hypothesized that increased local and borough concentration will be positively associated with VLT use.

Local concentration of VLTs can be operationalized as the spatial interaction between a respondent and the VLTs in his or her environment. The gravity model provides a good method for the estimation of local concentration. Spatial interaction, according to a gravity model, is a function of 1) the spatial separation of “origins” (respondents) and “destinations” (bars with VLTs), 2) characteristics which determine flow from various “origins” (individual-level determinants of VLT use as covered in section 2.2.3) and 3) characteristics of the destinations related to their “attractiveness” (likelihood that a given destination induces VLT use) (Bailey 1995, 338).

According to the gravity model the probability of interaction between a respondent and a VLT decreases monotonically with distance when all other factors are held constant, because of (1) the decreasing probability of knowing a VLT as distance to the VLT increases and (2) the increased effort, in terms of time and cost for the individual, as distance increases and (3) an increased number of intervening opportunities as distance increases (Sen 1995). Because distance is a proxy for knowledge and effort, one can deduce that places in the direction of one's workplace are more likely to be known, and also probably perceived as being relatively closer, as they can be frequented on the way home from work.

For the purposes of this paper, it is proposed to measure distance physically, in metres, and as a relative measure, with competing destinations. The first measure of distance, physical distance, is founded on the assumption that a person living physically closer to a VLT is more likely to use a VLT than a person living further from a VLT (assuming only establishments with VLTs exist). Thus, a person living in downtown Montreal is much more likely to use a VLT, since they are living in a higher density area with VLTs closer to their home. A second way of formulating the distance /concentration measure is to assume that each respondent has an equal probability of going to a bar. If all bars have VLTs then all people would be equally likely to use a VLT, no matter what the actual distance. In this scenario, bars without VLTs could be formulated as "intervening opportunities" with respect to VLT use, as they provide a similar service as a bar with a VLT, that is, they provide leisure and socialization, but without exposing their clients to VLTs. Thus, for rank based distance measures the probability of using a VLT is solely a function of the pattern of the types of liquor establishments (the number of VLTs they have) emanating from the respondent's residence.

Inverse distance weights attribute values by the distance separating an respondent from a liquor establishment (with or without VLTs). The local concentration function should be thought of as a mixture of the proximity to VLTs relative to the proximity to bars.

$$LC(x_i, e_i) = b_0 C(x_i, e_i^{VLT0}) + b_1 C(x_i, e_i^{VLT1}) + b_2 C(x_i, e_i^{VLT2+})$$

Equation 1. General form of the local concentration function

Note that b_0, b_1, b_2 are parameters estimated in the logistic regression model. e_i is a vector of the number of VLT licenses at each establishment beginning with the one closest to his or her home. The comma denotes that it spans the ranked distance of each establishment, i.e. $j=1 \dots n$ where n is the size of the neighbourhood (i.e. the width of the ranked distance matrix, in this case 200, see p. 21). $C(x_i, e_i^{VLT1})$ is a measure of the proximity of establishments with a single VLT license. e_i^{VLT1} is an indicator variable (i.e. a binary variable) corresponding to whether or not there is a VLT license at each of the 200 establishments, beginning with the one closest to the respondent's home.

$C(x_i, e_i^{VLT1})$ is an independent variable that is measured for each respondent.

For inverse distance it is the sum of the inverse distance to each establishment with a single VLT license. For inverse rank, this measure is the sum of the ranked distance to establishments with a single VLT license. To illustrate, suppose that a given respondent has a VLTL1 100m from his home, a VLTL0 200m from his home and a VLTL1 500m from his home. Then the inverse distance of sites with one VLT is

$$C_{ID}(x_i, e_i^{VLT1}) = (1) \frac{1}{0.1} + (0) \frac{1}{0.2} + (1) \frac{1}{0.5} = 12$$

and the inverse distance to sites with no VLT licenses is $C_{ID}(x_i, e_i^{VLT0}) = (0) \frac{1}{0.1} + (1) \frac{1}{0.2} + (0) \frac{1}{0.5} = 2$. On the other hand, the

inverse rank distance to sites with one VLT is

and the inverse rank distance to sites with

no VLTs is $C_{IR}(x_i, e_i^{VLT1}) = (0) \frac{1}{1} + (1) \frac{1}{2} + (0) \frac{1}{3} = \frac{1}{2}$. Thus, we see that each of the

three C_{IR} , can be calculated, for a single respondent, as the scalar multiplication of a

single vector of weights and an establishments binary variable. That is:

$$C(x_i, e_i^Z) = w_i \bullet e_i^Z$$

Equation 2. The concentration function

where e_i^Z describes any form of establishment binary variable and w_i is a matrix of

weights, in this case, either the inverse rank weights or inverse distance weights.

To obtain local concentration, the likelihood of VLT use is maximized with respect to the likelihood of the three concentration measures, yielding the estimates of b_0, b_1, b_2 . It is hypothesized that b_0 will be negative (i.e. an increase in VLTL0 proximity should lead to a decrease in probability of using a VLT), while b_1 and b_2 will be positive, with increased concentration leading to an increase in probability of use.

Note that in the case of inverse rank, the sum of the weights is equal for each respondent. The probability of using a VLT is solely a function of the pattern of establishments (and the number of VLTLs) emanating from the respondent's residence. In this special case, the b_0, b_1, b_2 are a linear combination of one another and thus b_0 can be removed. Thus, b_1, b_2 are expected to be positive, and represent the proximity of VLTL1 and VLTL2 relative to VLT0.

3.0.7 Borough Concentration

Measured as the proportion of bars in the borough that have VLTs. If there are no bars in the borough, a value of 0 is given.

3.0.8 Logistic Regression for estimation of influence of physical environment

The association between local concentration and the probability of using a VLT is measured using a logistic regression. The outcome, VLT use (used in last year (1) vs has not used(0)) is predicted using the two measures of local concentration (inverse distance and inverse rank). However, the composition of the population living in areas of differing levels of local concentration may differ. If VLT use is found to be associated with concentration, it may be due to the individual characteristics of the people living close to VLTs, and not their proximity to VLTs, that explains their increased propensity to use VLTs. Therefore, individual level controls are introduced to control for the differing composition of places with VLTs as opposed to places without VLTs.

3.0.9 Small Area Estimation

To test the hypothesis that VLT use clusters in boroughs, we must estimate the rate of use in each borough. Rates of VLT use for the small samples found in each borough are estimated using a multilevel model. In a multilevel model the mean of a cluster is estimated as a random effect (a deviation from global mean) that is proportional to the number of observations in the borough and the expected value of the observations in that borough. The expected value of the cluster mean is shrunk toward the grand expected value (the overall proportion) by a factor inversely proportional to the variance of the cluster mean (Longford 1993, 16-18 and 61). This is considered the optimal method for small area estimation (Rao 2003). In this study, penalized quasi-likelihood (PQL) from the package MASS supplied with R (Ihaka 1996) is the method of maximization used. Note that these models assume that the random effects are normally distributed and independent of the fixed-effects.

3.0.10 Estimation of neighbourhood-effects

Neighbourhood effects are estimates of the independent effects of neighbourhood on VLT use (Pickett and Pearl 2001). These are estimated in a similar fashion as the small area estimates, but incorporating controls for the composition of the boroughs. As with small area estimates, random-effects for each of the boroughs are obtained. The random effects, in this context, are the neighbourhood effects on VLT use.

4 RESULTS

VLT gambling is thought to be a function of individual and environmental characteristics. As was outlined earlier, the environmental considerations have been divided into aspects of the physical environment measured using a logistic regression and aspects of the social environment measured using a logistic regression with random effects for boroughs. A descriptive analysis of gambling covariates precedes the analysis of the social and physical environmental effects on VLT use.

4.1 *Bivariate analysis of gambling covariates*

To understand the relationships between VLT use, VLT distribution and characteristics of the respondent, an analysis of bivariate relationships within the dataset was conducted using contingency tables. The bivariate analysis aimed to determine which variables to introduce as controls in the analysis of social environment and in the analysis of geographic accessibility on use. No formal tests of significance of the relationships discussed below are presented.

Table 1 shows for each social group, the proportion using a VLT and the proportion living in the highest quintile of local VLT concentration. Borough concentration is not shown because it was not significantly related to VLT use. The following variables were related to VLT use and local concentration:

- Age: young adults are more likely to gamble and are less likely to live near VLTs
- Education: university educated are half as likely to use VLTs and live in places less concentrated with VLTs
- Lower-middle income respondents are more likely to gamble and more likely to live near VLTs

Furthermore, the following characteristics were not linked to living nearer, or further from VLTs, but were strongly linked to VLT use:

- Immigrants are less than half as likely to gamble, but do not live closer or further from VLTs.

Note that in other analyses, it was shown that anglophones are more likely to use VLTs and live in boroughs with fewer VLTs (compared to francophones and allophones).

However, in terms of local concentration, they live neither closer nor further from VLTs than the rest of the population.

Variable	Category	N	VLT use in last year				Local Concentration				
			Yes	No	%	OR*	Low	Mid	High	%**	OR***
Global			166	1841	8.3	Refer	662	662	683	34.0	Refer
Borough Uptake	Low	558	47	511	8.4	1.02	401	116	74	12.5	0.37
	Mid	914	80	834	8.8	1.06	210	357	347	38.0	1.12
	High	493	35	458	7.1	0.86	51	188	254	51.5	1.51
Local Proximity	Low	662	42	620	6.3	0.77	401	116	74	12.5	0.37
	Mid	662	60	602	9.1	1.10	210	357	347	38.0	1.12
	High	683	64	619	9.4	1.13	51	188	254	51.5	1.51
Age	18 to 24	259	46	213	17.8	2.11 +	94	88	77	29.7	0.87
	25 to 44	880	82	798	9.3	1.11 +	281	279	320	36.4	1.07
	45 +	728	33	695	4.5	0.54 -	287	295	286	32.9	0.97
Educational Attainment	* CEGEP or less	1351	139	1212	10.3	1.22 +	386	479	486	36.0	1.06
	University	656	27	629	4.1	0.49 -	276	183	197	30.0	0.88 -
Birth Place	* Canada	1450	147	1303	10.1	1.20 +	453	499	498	34.3	1.01
	Abroad	552	19	533	3.4	0.41 -	209	163	185	33.2	0.98
Mother Tongue	* English	301	36	265	12.0	1.42 +	372	441	448	35.5	1.04
	French	1261	110	1151	8.7	1.04	147	76	78	25.9	0.76 -
	Other	445	20	425	4.5	0.53 -	143	145	157		1.04
Occupation	Employed	1308	131	1177	10.0	1.19 +	414	434	460	35.2	1.03
	Student	195	18	177	9.2	1.10	80	56	59	30.3	0.89
	EI	44	4	40	9.1	1.08	13	12	19	43.2	1.27
	Health	43	4	39	9.3	1.10	17	14	12	27.9	0.82
	Retired	253	8	245	3.2	0.38 -	89	86	78	30.8	0.91
	Homemaker	118	1	117	0.8	0.10 -	39	40	39	33.1	0.97
	Maternity Leave	25	0	25	0.0	0.00	5	12	8	32.0	0.94
	Other Emp	16	0	16	0.0	0.00	5	7	4	25.0	0.73
Home Ownership	Owner	689	28	661	4.1	0.48 -	251	212	226	32.8	0.96
	Not Owner	1307	136	1171	10.4	1.24 +	411	450	457	34.7	1.02
Income among Employed	* <30k	335	37	298	11.0	1.34 +	82	118	135	40.3	1.18 +
	[30k,40k)	175	30	145	17.1	2.07 +	46	61	68	38.9	1.14 +
	[40k,60k)	288	30	258	10.4	1.26 +	91	96	101	35.1	1.03
	60k<	316	22	294	7.0	0.84 -	113	106	97	30.7	0.90 -
	NA	194	12	182	6.6	0.80 -	83	53	59	30.7	0.89 -

* The odds of using a VLT relative to the mean of the population

** The portion of respondents in the top tertile of concentration

*** The odds of being in the top tertile of concentration.

Table 1. Bivariate relation between VLT use, local concentration and individual risk factors.

4.2 *The distribution of VLT use across boroughs*

The aim of this section is to determine whether an equal proportion of each borough (N=49) gambles, or whether, as hypothesized, there are different mean rates of VLT use across boroughs. As well, we asked whether the proportion of the members of special subpopulations using VLTs varies across boroughs. The interest here is to describe the distribution of gamblers, to help identify areas where there may be many problem gamblers. Note that in the following section, we aim to confirm that these variations in rates of use can be attributed to so-called “neighbourhood effects”, or whether the variations in rates of use are an artifact of the composition of the boroughs.

The estimated variances from the small area estimates model (Table 3) indicate that the proportion of borough members gambling varies significantly across boroughs. The variance component ratio (VCR), a measure of the portion of the variance that can be attributed to the borough level relative to the total variance (Longford 1993), is approximately 9%. Recall that the VCR ratio can be interpreted as the importance of random effects (i.e. variation in the rates of use across boroughs) compared to within-group error (variation of rates of use across individuals within a borough). A between borough variance of 9% is considered quite large. The lower bound of the between borough variance 95% confidence interval is 2% indicating that the variance is statistically significant (there is only a 2.5% chance that the between borough-variance is less than 2%). Proportions gambling within specific subpopulations were especially variable across boroughs.

- Gender delimited subpopulations showed significant and high VCRs, estimated at 23% for men and 30% for women.

- Gender-age delimited subpopulations showed significant and high VCRs, ranging from 33% for older men, to 61% for older women.¹
- Proportions of english mother tongue varied significantly across boroughs, with an estimated VCR of 30%, while proportions of Francophones did not.
- Proportions of immigrants and Canadian-born did not show significant variations across boroughs. Especially, proportions of university educated gambling showed almost no variation across boroughs.

Variable	Category	Variance estimated	95% CI		VCR*
			low er	upper	
Mean	(Intercept)	0.13	0.02	0.65	0.12
	Within-group var	0.96			
Age	18-24	0.00	0.00	>10	0.00
	25-44	0.17	0.02	1.57	0.15
	45+	0.02	0.00	>10	0.02
	Within-group var	1.02			
Birth Place	Canada	0.12	0.02	0.65	0.11
	Abroad	0.31	0.01	7.01	0.25
	Residual	0.92			
Edu Attain	CEGEP or less	0.14	0.02	0.86	0.12
	University	0.02	0.00	>10	0.02
	Within-group var	1.00			
Mother Tongue	French	0.09	0.01	0.72	0.09
	English	0.34	0.03	3.75	0.26
	Within-group var	0.96			
Sex	Male	0.26	0.08	0.87	0.25
	Female	0.64	0.20	2.08	0.45
	Within-group var	0.79			
Male	18-24	0.34	0.04	3.22	0.43
	25-44	0.90	0.41	1.97	0.67
	45+	0.28	0.04	2.01	0.38
Female	18-24	1.30	0.39	4.30	0.74
	25-44	0.45	0.08	2.54	0.50
	45+	1.70	0.66	4.40	0.79
	Within-group var	0.69			

*VCR = variance component ratio

Table 2. Estimated variances of mean VLT use, for different subpopulations within boroughs.

¹The distribution of the borough-level random effects for women 25-44 and 45+ are non-normally distributed, therefore estimates of rates of use may be inappropriate as the estimated variance may be inflated.

Table 3 shows the shrunken estimates of proportion gambling for the whole population as well as for the specific subpopulations in the 49 boroughs. Maps of the estimated VLT use are presented in the following figures. Comments:

- Generally, low mean rates of use among residents of the boroughs within the old city of Montreal, with the exception of the Plateau-Centre-Sud, where rates of use are high, especially among women (10.3%) (see figure 4).
- A large proportion of men gambled in the east end, as well as in the north-east, e.g. Pointe-aux-Trembles, Rivière-des-Prairies (25%), Montréal-Nord (27%) and Anjou (20%) showed elevated rates of VLT use among men. In these same boroughs, rates of gambling among women were below the average of 5.1% among women. e.g. Pointe-aux-Trembles, Rivière-des-Prairies (2.9%), Montréal-Nord (4.1%) and Anjou (3.5%). On the other hand, rates of gambling among young women seemed to be higher in the central boroughs of the Plateau Mont Royal (20.4%), Ville-Marie (20.6%) and Saint-Henri (20.8%) (see figure 5).
- Across the study area, 3% of older women gambled. However, note that in Côte-Saint-Luc (CSL) 23% of older women gambled. To a lesser extent, this pattern carried over to women in the adjacent boroughs of Lasalle (10.3%), Lachine (6.2%) and Verdun (5%) (see figure 9).

As can be seen above most of the estimated rates of use show a strong degree of spatial autocorrelation across boroughs. The exception seems to be the rates of use among people of english mother tongue, which seemed to vary stochastically with respect to space (see figure 10).

ID	Borough	Region	Respondents	Users	All groups	Men	Women	Men 18 - 24	Men 25 - 44	Men 45 +	Women 18 - 24	Women 25 - 44	Women 45 +	Anglophone
	Whole Study Area		2007	166	8.3	13.1	5.1	30.5	16.7	5.5	13.1	4.3	3.0	13.9
1	Anjou	E	42	4	9.5	19.7	3.5	46.4	38.4	4.7	10.7	3.3	2.1	12.6
2	Baie-d'Urfé	W	3	0	9.0	12.3	5.0	30.5	14.6	5.4	13.1	4.3	2.8	12.1
3	Beaconsfield	W	9	2	10.2	20.5	4.5	46.4	14.6	8.7	13.1	4.0	2.6	19.8
4	Côte-Saint-Luc	C	21	4	11.0	12.7	11.4	30.5	22.3	4.8	12.1	4.2	22.8	19.8
5	Dollard-des-Ormeaux	W	41	4	9.5	16.8	3.8	42.0	14.4	7.0	11.3	3.5	2.2	17.7
6	Dorval	W	18	0	8.1	10.0	4.4	26.8	10.2	5.0	12.1	4.0	2.5	9.6
7	Hampstead	C	4	0	8.9	12.3	4.9	30.5	16.7	5.2	13.1	4.1	3.0	12.6
8	Ile-Bizard	W	14	1	9.0	13.0	4.6	26.8	25.4	4.9	13.1	4.1	2.6	18.5
9	Kirkland	W	15	4	11.6	14.2	12.2	46.4	13.0	5.1	28.7	4.1	9.3	34.8
10	Lachine	W	34	4	10.0	16.9	5.2	26.8	58.0	4.5	11.3	3.5	6.2	14.5
11	Lasalle	W	69	5	8.7	8.4	8.3	46.4	6.0	4.2	13.1	5.4	10.5	15.4
12	Auteuil	L	30	3	9.5	14.5	4.3	35.0	17.6	4.9	12.1	3.8	2.5	19.7
13	Chomedey	L	72	8	10.3	16.5	5.5	47.4	17.4	6.2	11.3	8.7	1.8	19.8
14	Duvernay	L	21	3	10.1	15.4	6.1	26.8	29.8	7.0	13.1	8.0	2.3	13.9
15	Fabreville	L	22	1	8.5	11.5	4.4	30.5	13.6	5.0	13.1	3.7	2.6	13.2
16	Laval-des-Rapides	L	25	3	9.8	14.6	5.9	21.9	31.0	5.0	20.8	3.8	2.4	13.9
17	Laval-Ouest	L	9	0	8.6	11.3	4.7	30.5	11.9	5.2	12.1	4.0	3.0	13.9
18	Laval-sur-le-Lac	L	4	0	8.9	12.3	4.9	30.5	16.7	5.2	12.1	4.2	3.0	13.2
19	Pont-Viau	L	11	2	10.1	18.1	4.6	46.4	36.6	5.0	13.1	4.1	2.6	13.9
20	Sainte-Dorothee	L	25	2	9.1	13.8	4.3	31.4	18.2	4.9	12.1	3.7	2.5	11.6
21	Sainte-Rose	L	22	2	9.3	11.8	6.2	26.8	16.7	4.9	23.3	4.0	2.5	13.2
22	Saint-Francois	L	15	2	9.8	11.3	8.6	26.8	13.0	5.2	11.3	11.8	2.8	13.2
23	Saint-Vincent-de-Paul	L	11	2	10.1	14.6	6.6	30.5	29.8	5.1	13.1	7.6	2.7	13.9
24	Vimont	L	11	1	9.2	15.1	4.5	39.8	16.7	5.2	12.1	4.3	2.4	13.9
25	Ahuntsic / Cartierville	C	129	7	7.5	9.2	4.4	15.7	16.7	4.3	13.5	2.9	3.2	12.1
26	Côte-des-Neiges / Notre-Dame-de-Grâce	C	159	8	7.1	8.5	4.5	22.0	11.6	3.2	16.4	3.7	1.5	9.4
27	Mercier / Hochelaga-Maisonneuve	C	116	12	10.3	17.0	4.5	52.3	9.3	9.7	10.1	6.1	1.7	13.5
28	Plateau-Mont-Royal / Centre-Sud	C	155	18	11.3	13.3	10.1	22.0	14.1	7.3	20.4	9.2	4.1	22.6
29	Rivière-des-Prairies / Pointe-aux-Trembles	C	91	11	11.0	25.6	2.9	52.8	25.2	12.6	10.7	2.8	1.6	18.5
30	Rosemont / Petite-Patrie	C	147	13	9.4	15.8	4.4	17.6	26.6	6.5	17.2	3.5	1.5	11.2
31	Sud-Ouest	C	73	4	8.0	8.2	6.6	26.2	6.4	4.2	20.8	7.2	1.8	11.5
32	Ville-Marie	C	70	4	8.1	8.6	6.6	22.7	7.1	4.4	20.6	3.0	4.8	10.9
33	Villeray / Saint-Michel / Parc-Extension	C	136	1	5.3	5.9	2.5	22.7	3.9	3.7	6.2	2.6	1.6	10.5
34	Montréal-Est	E	3	0	9.0	12.3	5.0	30.5	13.0	5.5	13.1	4.3	2.8	13.9
35	Montréal-Nord	C	63	9	11.6	27.2	4.1	31.8	69.0	6.8	9.2	5.1	1.9	12.6
36	Montréal-Ouest	C	3	0	9.0	12.3	5.0	30.5	16.7	5.2	13.1	4.2	3.0	13.2
37	Mont-Royal	C	19	1	8.7	13.8	4.1	30.5	29.8	4.9	12.1	4.0	2.3	15.8
38	Outremont	C	26	2	9.0	14.2	4.1	24.1	20.0	7.2	12.1	4.0	2.3	12.1
39	Pierrefonds	W	38	3	9.0	11.9	5.5	46.4	7.4	6.6	10.7	4.0	5.9	12.2
40	Pointe-Claire	W	18	0	8.1	9.8	4.5	30.5	10.2	4.8	13.1	4.2	2.4	9.6
41	Roxboro	W	4	0	8.9	11.6	5.1	30.5	13.0	5.2	13.1	4.3	3.0	13.2
42	Sainte-Anne-de-Bellevue	W	8	0	8.6	11.9	4.6	30.5	16.7	5.1	13.1	4.1	2.6	10.8
43	Sainte-Geneviève	W	8	0	8.6	11.9	4.6	30.5	14.6	5.2	13.1	3.7	3.0	13.2
44	Saint-Laurent	C	71	4	8.1	10.7	4.3	20.2	9.7	8.0	12.1	3.1	4.4	8.7
45	Saint-Léonard	E	49	6	10.4	17.2	5.1	21.9	32.0	6.5	12.1	3.2	6.5	25.0
46	Saint-Pierre	W	2	1	9.9	16.3	5.1	30.5	29.8	5.5	13.1	4.3	3.0	13.9
47	Senneville	W	1	0	9.1	13.1	5.0	30.5	16.7	5.5	13.1	4.3	2.8	13.9
48	Verdun	C	56	4	8.7	13.6	4.4	26.8	20.0	6.3	9.6	3.2	5.0	9.6
49	Westmount	C	14	1	9.0	11.9	6.0	30.5	14.6	5.2	13.1	7.6	2.3	13.5

Table 3. The prevalence of VLT use in the last year (%)

Figure 4. Prevalence of VLT use across Montreal boroughs (N=49)

Figure 5. Prevalence of VLT use among gender subgroups across Montreal boroughs (N=49)

Figure 6. Prevalence of VLT use among men 18 – 24 across Montreal boroughs (N=49)

Figure 7. Prevalence of VLT use among women 18 – 24 across Montreal boroughs (N=49)

Figure 8. Prevalence of VLT use among men 18 – 24 across Montreal boroughs (N=49)

Figure 9. Prevalence of VLT use among women 45 + across Montreal boroughs (N=49)

* English mother tongue to be more precise

Figure 10. Prevalence of VLT use among Anglophones across Montreal boroughs (N=49)

4.3 Neighbourhood effects on VLT use

To uncover independent area-effects on probability of VLT use, individual controls must be introduced to control for the differing propensities of individuals in each borough to gamble (Pickett 2001). That is, the differing rates of use across boroughs may be attributable to the composition of the boroughs.

This analysis will incorporate only one of the random effects structures discussed in section 4.3, sex. In section 4.3, we saw that the division of the population into gender

subgroups was associated with the largest VCRs, indicating that rates of use seem to vary differently for men and women across boroughs. A logistic regression model incorporating both individual-level (fixed effects) and borough level (random effects) parameters was estimated. In total six critical individual-level controls were chosen to test whether the neighbourhood effects for gender subgroups existed. In effect, what we are testing is whether the variations in prevalence of use among gender subgroups (as tested in section 4.2) were significantly decreased by the introduction of individual level controls. These controls consisted of : age, birthplace, mother tongue, sex, educational attainment and home ownership. Table 4 shows the estimated odds ratios and the estimated variances of the prevalence of VLT use. The estimates of the variance component ratios for men and women have decreased, relative to the model with no controls (see Table 2 on p.32) signifying that the composition of the boroughs with high rates of use are somewhat different. Figure 11 shows the relative odds (random-effects²) before and after the introduction of individual-level controls. The random effects seem to be normally distributed, and the random effects of this model incorporating individual controls are generally smaller than that of the model without individual controls. Nevertheless, the variances remain significant and the variance component ratio remain high for the model incorporating individual controls.

² Note that the random-effects are on a log-scale, i.e. -0.5 is equal to and $e^{-0.5}=0.6$, a 40% reduction in the odds of using a VLT for respondents residing in that borough while a random effect of 0.5 is equal to an $e^{0.5}=1.64$, a 64% increase in the odds of using a VLT for respondents residing in that borough.

Variable	Category	Reference	Odds Ratio	p(OR=1)
VLT use	Uses	Does not use	0.07	**
Age	25 - 44	18-24	0.66	**
	45 +	18-24	0.29	**
Birth Place	Abroad	Canada	0.33	**
Mother Tongue	English	Other	1.82	**
Home Ownership	Not Owner	Owner	2.34	**
Sex	Male	Female	2.75	**
Educational Attainment	University	CEGEP or less	0.47	**
Between Group Variance		Variance (95% CI)	VCR	
Female		0.31 (0.06 - 1.7)	0.25	
Male		0.17 (0.04 - 0.31)	0.16	
Within Group Variance		0.92 (0.90 - 0.94)		

* p < .05, ** p < .01

Table 4. Odds of VLT use and variance of borough effects (N=49).

* see Table 3 on p.34

Figure 11. Relative odds of using a VLT for residents of 49 boroughs with and without controls for composition of boroughs.

In summary, there are statistically significant neighbourhood effects with respect to VLT use. The borough in which one resides does influence the probability of an individual in that borough using a VLT. The introduction of individual level controls had little influence on the interpretation of the random effects, they only attenuated the estimated variances slightly (the correlation between the random effects before and after the introduction of controls was 0.98 for women and 0.95 for men).

Furthermore, Figure 11 also shows that certain boroughs with strongly positive random-effects for men have negative random effects for women. We also noted this when observing the maps of VLT use for men and women (see p. 33 for the discussion of these results). The random-effects corresponding to male gambling and female gambling (logged odds ratios corresponding to each borough) are plotted below in Figure 12. Visually it seems that there may be a relation, with the exception of one outlier, corresponding to the borough of Parc-Extension, where the rate of VLT use is significantly lower for both men and women.

Figure 12. Relation between borough-level random-effects for men and women.

4.4 Concentration effects on VLT use

A normal logistic regression model (without random-effects) was used to measure the association between VLT usage and measures of VLT concentration, at both the borough level as well as at the local level. Borough concentration, measured by borough uptake, was not associated with VLT use. That is, respondents residing in boroughs where a higher proportion of bars had VLT licenses were not more likely to use VLTs than respondents living in boroughs where the uptake is lower.

Recall that both local concentration measures are sums of independent measures of concentration of sites with no VLT licenses, a single VLT license, or two or more licenses (see Equation 3 and Equation 4). These components of the local concentration measures were entered into two logistic regression models. The first logistic regression

model consisted of a model with VLT use as the dependent variable and with the three inverse distance concentration measures added as separate independent variables ($C_{VLT0}^{ID}, C_{VLT1}^{ID}$ and C_{VLT2+}^{ID}). Similarly, the second logistic regression model consisted of a model with VLT use as the dependent variable but with the two inverse rank concentration measures ($C_{VLT1}^{IR}, C_{VLT2+}^{IR}$) as independent variables. Overall, neither of these models was significant when tested using an likelihood ratio test of the residual deviances (a measure of overall fit analogous to the mean squared error). However, the signs of the coefficients were, as hypothesized, positive for increasing VLT1 and VLT2+ concentration (i.e. positive for the coefficients corresponding to $C_{VLT1}^{ID}, C_{VLT2+}^{ID}$ and $C_{VLT1}^{IR}, C_{VLT2+}^{IR}$) and negative for increasing VLT0 concentration (i.e. negative for the coefficient corresponding to C_{VLT0}^{ID}).

$$LC^{ID} = b_0^{ID} C_{VLT0}^{ID} + b_1^{ID} C_{VLT1}^{ID} + b_2^{ID} C_{VLT2+}^{ID}$$

Equation 3. Inverse distance local concentration

$$LC^{IR} = b_1^{IR} C_{VLT1}^{IR} + b_2^{IR} C_{VLT2+}^{IR}$$

Equation 4. Inverse rank local concentration

The separate independent variables making up inverse distance (3 different independent variables) and inverse rank (2 different independent variables) were summed into their respective local concentration measures. This was a weighted sum, with weights corresponding to the b 's in Equation 3 and Equation 4. These b 's are the estimates from the two logistic regression models described in the preceding paragraph. LC^{IR} and LC^{ID} were then converted into categorical variables by splitting the continuous variables into tertiles.

LC^{IR} was significant when the upper two tertiles of VLT use were merged, while LC^{ID} was not significant. From this point on, local concentration is used interchangeably with concentration measured by inverse rank. When controls for the composition of the neighbourhoods close to VLTs are taken, the effect of local concentration becomes only marginally significant. Table 5 summarizes the results of these models.

The residents residing in the highest tertile of inverse rank concentration were 50% more likely to use VLTs than the rest of the sample. After controls for the composition of the high concentration areas were taken, concentration became marginally significant with a significance level of 0.07. After introduction of these controls, the residents residing in the highest tertile of inverse rank concentration were 33% more likely to use VLTs than the rest of the sample. Given that the large number of controls introduced only slightly influenced the estimated association between residing near a VLT and gambling (there where no individual variables that were extremely strong confounders), the overall effect of local concentration is deemed to be significant.

Variable	Category	Reference	Odds Ratio	p(OR) = 1
Base			0.07	**
Local Concentration	Highest 2 tertiles	Lowest tertile	1.50	*
Base			0.04	**
Local Concentration	Highest 2 tertiles	Lowest tertile	1.33	0.07
Age	25 - 44	18-24	0.47	**
	45 +	18-24	0.25	**
Birth Place	Abroad	Canada	0.33	**
Household Income	Earnings [0,30k)	Not employed	1.90	**
	Earnings [30k,40k)	Not employed	3.56	**
	Earnings [40k,60k)	Not employed	2.32	**
	Earnings [60k,	Not employed	1.76	*
Mother Tongue	English	Other	1.91	**
Home Ownership	Not Owner	Owner	2.12	**
Sex	Male	Female	2.57	**
Educational Attainment	University	CEGEP or less	0.46	**

* p < .05, ** p < .01

Table 5. Influence of local and borough concentration.

Figure 13 is a map of local concentration across the study area. Note that downtown and the west island are generally low concentration, while the east, north and Laval all tend to be in the upper two-thirds of local concentration.

Figure 13. The distribution of local concentration across the islands of Montreal and Laval.

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Distribution of VLT users in Montreal

A single grand mean of VLT use does not adequately describe the rate of VLT use within the different boroughs. Instead, rates of VLT use vary across boroughs. Variations in rates of use are stronger for subgroups, especially gender subgroups. The high portion of residents susceptible to gambling problems among certain place-based subgroups suggest that community intervention may be a warranted method of combating gambling problems. Most notably, men in the East end were much more likely to gamble.

5.2 Neighbourhood effects on VLT use

The significant variations in rates of use for men and women, despite the introduction of controls for the composition of the neighbourhoods, indicate that there are neighbourhood effects on VLT use. These findings confirm those of researchers who have used multilevel models to examine neighbourhood effects on health behaviours (Pickett and Pearl, 2001).

The neighbourhood effects for men and women were significantly negatively related. This study is somewhat exceptional as studies using multilevel models have not comparatively studied male and female behaviour (Pickett and Pearl, 2001). Concentrated VLT use by men is associated with low female VLT use prevalence. Dixey (1987) showed that women play bingo because it gives them an opportunity to socialize with other women. In this case, it is suspected that bars in those places with high rates of male VLT use are more likely to be male-only places of socialization. Given that women are not welcome in such places, they would not have access to VLTs, explaining their lower rates of VLT use. On the other hand, in the boroughs of the Plateau and Ville-Marie, where rates of use for men and women are more similar (i.e. elevated for women and average or below average for men), bars are more accessible to women. That is, establishments near

downtown may be less old, less likely to be taverns, and are more likely to cater to both sexes.

5.3 *Concerning Local VLT concentration*

The evidence confirms the hypothesis that local VLT concentration positively contributes to probability of using a VLT. We can ascertain that the portion of the population living in the highest 2/3 of the local concentration scale are about 50% more likely to use VLTs than the rest of the population. Although this relation is attenuated by the introduction of individual-level controls for composition, the relationship remains statistically significant.

The gravity model formulation proved valuable for formulating measures of physical accessibility. For the case of VLT use, the rank distance local concentration measure was more applicable than local concentration measured by physical distance. While in this case only bars with no VLTs were operationalized as intervening opportunities, other intervening opportunities could be used in future research. Given that gambling is thought to be related to boredom proneness (Blaszczynski et al. 2002), all features of the environment that offer boredom relief without exposing one to VLTs could become intervening opportunities with respect to VLT use.

In terms of policy, local distribution of VLT opportunities influence the rate of VLT use, suggesting that community interventions mentioned in the section 5.1 should include bar owners as important players. Bars without VLTs can be considered sinks with respect to rates of VLT use, while bars with more than a single VLT license seem to be strong contributors to local VLT use. Furthermore, these results suggest that municipal policy prohibiting liquor licenses does not prevent VLT use among local residents, since such policy does not increase the number of intervening opportunities (i.e. the number of bars with no VLT licenses between the resident and a bar with VLTs). Instead, creating

alternative opportunities that are less unhealthy (like bars with no VLTs) may be more likely to reduce use.

With respect to the current debate over the placement of VLTs in fewer more concentrated outlets, the results are less clear. Such a concentration of VLTs into larger establishments would certainly increase the number of intervening opportunities for the average resident (this would decrease the probability of using a VLT). However, these establishments may also have a much stronger influence on the local populations and a wider range of influence (due to more advertising, etc). The evidence here suggests that the rate of use among those living near the hypothetical “mini-casinos” would increase significantly, while for the rest of the population, they would decrease. Overall, it could not be determined whether rates of use would increase or decrease.

5.4 Limitations

5.4.0.1 Distance measurements

Ideally the exact road network distance would be used, because this represents the actual distances travelled by the respondents when going to a bar. However, the straightline distance was used as an approximation. This could introduce a bias in the distance measurements. In particular, those residing close to large road network discontinuities, such as along the rivers’ edge, could have measures of distance that do not correlate to the travelled distance. Exact road network distance was attempted due to fear of bias, however, current algorithms implemented in GIS software packages ArcGIS 8, and ArcView 3, were incapable of handling the required matrix size.

A subsample of the shortest network paths was calculated in ArcView 3. The Arcview extension called Shortest Network Path (V 1.1) with the 2001 Census Road Network File (StatsCan 2001) were used to calculate network distances along the census

road network file. The correlation between the subsample of network paths vs the straightline distance was 0.9.

6 CONCLUSION

This study has shown that VLT use is influenced by multiple factors, related to both the individual and the environment in which he or she lives. While the individual factors related to gambling behaviour have often been studied, ecological factors have generally been neglected. However, it is evident that the distribution of local gambling opportunities and the neighbourhood both influence the propensity for individuals to use VLTs.

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